
A COMPOSITE MODEL OF LIBRARIAN LEADERSHIP CAPACITY

Project Site: <https://libraryleadership.hcommons.org/capacity/>

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Overview

Roles: Navigator, Experimenter, People Developer, Relations Builder	
Competencies	Personal Attributes
Cognitive <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem Solving• Decision Making• Reflective Thinking Vision <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Creativity• Holistic Thinking• Forward Thinking Interpersonal <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Communication Skills• Cultural Competence• Accountability• Team Building• Inspiring or Motivating Others Managerial <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Change Management• Resource Management• Strategic Planning• Collaboration• Flexibility and Adaptability	Emotional Skills <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Social Awareness / Empathy• Emotional Resilience• Self Awareness Self-view <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Self Confidence / Self Efficacy• Leader Identity Moral Values <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Integrity• Respectfulness Personalities <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Agreeableness• Perseverance

Leadership Roles

Navigator

- The role to set directions for the collective, and make decisions for the collective

Experimenter

- The role to try new ideas in uncertainties; to take intelligent risks, to create a failure-tolerant environment

People Developer

- The role to create opportunities to grow people and develop staff, to view development of staff as an integral part in the growth of the organization, to view development for staff as important as other organization missions

Relations Builder

- The role to enhance working relations, through building trust and building mutual understanding

Competencies

The elements originate from the [competency model of Ammons-Stephen et al](#), with modification in the labels and descriptions. Sixteen competencies are grouped into 4 domains:

Cognitive – the ability to process ideas

Problem-Solving

- identify what a problem is, and identify key factors for solving the problem
- solve problems in a thorough, yet timely manner
- step back from a situation in order to suggest an objective solution
- foster an environment that encourages others to create solutions

Decision Making

- assume responsibility for your decisions
- act decisively, making sound and timely decisions
- show transparency in decision making

Reflective Thinking

- assess shortcomings and assets of the organization
- recognize and implement opportunities for continuous improvement

- reflect on your experiences to evaluate failure, success and lessons

Vision – the ability to see beyond

Creativity

- able to come up with non-traditional, unconventional ideas
- foster creativity and innovation by encouraging inventive thoughts and experimentation
- have innovative approach to the mission and goals of the team or organization

Holistic Thinking

- able to see beyond yourself and the scope of your unit
- consider the impact of your team or organization in the greater community and beyond
- consider ideas, environments, and technologies that impact communities and the institution on a broader scale

Forward Thinking

- able to see beyond the current situation
- show foresight by anticipating problems as well as opportunities
- exhibit the ability to envision both positive and negative consequences
- inspire others to think creatively about what might be, rather than just what is

Interpersonal – the ability to create a positive atmosphere with / for other people

Communication Skills

- practice active listening
- articulate ideas effectively through verbal and written communication
- adopt effective strategies to communicate with supervisors, peers and subordinates; and with users and collaborators
- give and receive constructive feedback
- withhold judgment
- encourage an environment of active communication

Cultural Competence

- exhibit an awareness of and appreciation for diverse cultures and beliefs
- foster an environment where all cultures are respected and valued

Accountability

- build trust in others
- lead by example
- assume responsibility for decisions made

Team Building

- build relationships inside and outside the team and the organization

- promote and encourage strategic team-building
- foster a culture that values innovation and creativity
- effectively delegate tasks and responsibilities

Inspiring and Motivating Others

- inspire others to succeed
- motivate others to actively contribute to the organization
- create an environment of trust and integrity
- build and provide ongoing support for staff
- encourage a developmental climate

Managerial – the ability to handle managerial tasks effectively

Change Management

- build internal and external support for change
- work with others to keep transitions and changes running smoothly
- willing to take calculated risks

Resource Management

- understand the types of resources you have (e.g. financial resources, human resources, organizational resources)
- understand cost efficiency and effectiveness
- apportion and distribute resources equitably and fairly
- assign projects to colleagues and employees in a constructive way
- act with diligence and care

Strategic Planning

- identify clear, well-defined goals and outcomes
- exhibit short-term and long-term planning capabilities
- able to implement plans to drive results

Collaboration

- are tactful to “give and take” with collaborators
- build relationships with community groups and constituents
- work with others where sharing resources would be appropriate

Flexibility and Adaptability

- exhibit an open mind to new ideas
- able to accept views different from yourself
- maintain a level head through difficult situations

Personal Attributes

Emotional Skills

Social Awareness / Empathy

- able to recognize, understand and feel other people's emotions and feelings

Emotional Resilience

- able to cope with stressful situations
- aware of emotional challenges and accept it without being overwhelmed

Self Awareness

- recognize how your feelings affect you and job performance
- understand your strengths and weaknesses

Self-View

Self Confidence / Self Efficacy

- have trust in your knowledge and competence
- believe in your ability to handle situations

Leader Identity

- see yourself as a leader
- consider a leader role as a central part of your professional functions

Moral Values

Integrity

- are fair and honest
- take personal responsibility
- put words in actions

Respectfulness

- respect effort and contributions that other people make; able to show that appreciation appropriately
- are humble and modest

Personalities

Agreeableness

- kind, considerate and generous
- have a general concern for social harmony

- value getting along with others;
- trusting and trustworthy, helpful, and willing to compromise your interests with others

Perseverance

- have patience
- able to face difficult situations with calmness and patience
- have the determination to achieve goals in spite of setbacks